

J-Band induced in Pseudoisocyanine by Polyanion of High Charge Density^ψ

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Induction of J-band in *N,N'*-diethylpseudoisocyanine chloride (PIC) depended primarily on the suitable conformation of the polyanion in addition to its charge density. PIC failed to exhibit J-band with Bael (*Aegle marmelos*) exudate gum polysaccharide, BP (charge density 0.19 per monosaccharide unit) and Bael fruit gum polysaccharide, AMA (charge density 0.074). Unlike the failure of chondroitin 4-sulphate (CS-4, charge density 1.0) to exhibit J-band chondroitin 6-sulphate (CS-6, charge density 1.0), Heparin (Hep, charge density 1.5) and dextran sulphate (DS, charge density 2.0) exhibited sharp red shifted J-band in PIC ($1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$). The stoichiometry of polyanion-dye compounds was found to be ~ 2 : 1 for the systems exhibiting J-band. Ethanol concentrations needed to reverse the exhibition of J-band were 40, 30 and 20% for PIC-DS (P/D = 3.0), PIC-Hep (P/D = 10.0) and PIC-CS-6 (P/D = 42.0) systems respectively.

We reported earlier the metachromatic interactions of dimethyl methylene blue, methylene blue and toluidine blue¹ and also of pinacyanol chloride² with polyanionic polysaccharides of varying charge densities, including the effect of disruptive factors like ethanol, urea etc. on the different systems. Since exhibition of J-band was reported to be sharply influenced by charge densities³⁻⁵ of polyanions and stoichiometry of polyanion-dye compounds⁴, we report here our observations on interactions of PIC with the acid polysaccharides and on the stoichiometry of its compounds with polyanions. Effects of ethanol/urea on the J-aggregates of the different systems have also been studied.

Results and Discussion

N,N'-Diethylpseudoisocyanine chloride (PIC) is non-planar⁶ and forms twisted and staggered aggregate⁷ resulting in red-shifted J-band⁸ instead of blue-shifted metachromasia associated with stacking of dye cations. Exhibition of J-band by PIC depends on the nature and conformation of polyanion⁹. J-aggregation of cyanine dye has been reported to

be caused by polyanions having not too high charge density⁴.

Bael fruit polysaccharide AMA (eq. wt. 2055), Chalta fruit polysaccharide DI (eq. wt. 996) and Bael exudate gum polysaccharide BP (eq. wt. 854) failed to exhibit J-band in PIC.

It is obvious that for associated spectral change, red- or blue-shift, in dyes bound on polyanions, a big distance of separation between the bound dyes will be an unfavourable condition. AMA and BP have low charge densities (0.074 and 0.19 per monosaccharide unit respectively) and the successive anionic groups will be separated by large distance in stretched conformation of the polymers. The practical identity of the spectrum of the dye alone with the spectrum with AMA and BP (Fig. 1B and C) and also with DI (curve not shown) show that even in the possible coil conformation of the polysaccharides in the aqueous solution, the bound dye cations do not overlap favourably to cause any appreciable spectral change. Bean *et al.*³ reported exhibition of J-band in the dye 4,5,4',5',4,5,4',5'-

^ψA part of the work was accepted for presentation at the Fourth Asian Chemical Congress held at Beijing, 1991.

dibenzo-3,3'-diethyl-9-methylthiocarbocyanine by a partially esterified polyacid polysaccharide and not by the acid itself. This suggested that for staggered aggregation of cyanine dye cations a somewhat larger distance between the anionic sites would be favourable.

Unlike the failure of chondroitin 4-sulphate (charge density 1.0) to cause J-aggregation of PIC¹⁰, chondroitin 6-sulphate (charge density same as the chondroitin 4-sulphate) used in the present investigation exhibited sharp J-band with PIC ($1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$), the intensity of J-band increased progressively with the increase of polymer to dye concentration (P/D) at least up to the value of 42.0 (Fig. 1D).

Fig 1 Absorption spectra of $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ pseudoisocyanine chloride (PIC) in (A) water, (B) in presence of AMA at P/D = 20.0, (C) BP at P/D = 20.0, (D) CS at P/D = 42.0, (E) Hep at P/D = 10.0 and (F) DS at P/D = 3.0

Induction of J-band by PIC can, therefore, reasonably be attributed primarily to the suitable conformation of the polyanion facilitating staggered aggregation of dye cations in addition to being influenced by its charge density. Heparin (charge density 1.50) induced J-aggregation of PIC, the intensity of J-band increased progressively with P/D up to the value of 10.0 (Fig. 1E) and then decreased (figure not shown). J-band exhibiting capacity of PIC was also retained with dextran sulphate (DS), a polyanion with fairly high charge density (2.0).

DS induced very sharp J-band in PIC, the intensity of J-band being maximum at P/D = 3.0 (Fig. 1F). The intensity of J-band then progressively decreased with the increase of P/D (figure not shown).

It was reported that polyanions capable of inducing J-band in PIC formed compounds with it in the stoichiometry of 2 : 1. Polyacrylic acid though formed compound with PIC in the stoichiometry of 2 : 1, it failed to induce distinct J-band in PIC. Sodium salt of polyacrylic acid however, formed a complex with PIC with a stoichiometry of 2 : 1 and exhibited very sharp J-band over a wide range of P/D⁴. CS, Hep and DS, despite variation in charge densities, induced sharp J-band in PIC and formed compounds with it in the stoichiometry of ~ 2 : 1 (Table 1). This suggests that very close packing of dye cations on the polyanion does not favour formation of J-aggregate by PIC though relative overlapping of dye cations with the polyanions increases in order, CS < Hep < DS.

TABLE 1—STOICHIOMETRY OF PSEUDOISOCYANINE-POLYANION COMPOUNDS*

Polyanion	Charge density	Stoichiometry	Observation
BP	0.19	0.99	No J-band
CS	1.00	2.00	J-band
Hep	1.50	2.00	J-band
DS	2.00	1.90	J-band

* Method Conductometric titration

Reversal of J-band with ethanol/urea grades the stability of J-aggregate. Ethanol concentrations needed to reverse the exhibition of J-band were found to be 40, 30 and 20% for PIC-DS (P/D = 3.0), PIC-Hep (P/D = 10.0) and PIC-CS (P/D = 42.0) systems respectively (Fig. 2). P/D values corresponded to the maximum intensity of J-band for the respective systems. Similar trends were also observed with added urea on the different systems (figure not shown). This suggests that particular conformation of a polyanion though dictates staggered aggregation of PIC, charge density of the polyanion also plays an important role by facilitating strong electrostatic bonding between dye cations and polyanions leading to the stability of the J-aggregate.

Fig 2. Variation of J-band intensity of $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ PIC in presence of (A) DS at P/D = 3.0, (B) Hep at P/D = 10.0 and (C) CS at P/D = 42.0 with per cent ethanol (v/v).

Experimental

Sources of Bael exudate gum polysaccharide (BP), Bael fruit gum polysaccharide (AMA), dextran sulphate (DS), chondroitin sulphate (CS) and heparin (Hep) were described earlier². Pseudoisocyanine chloride (PIC) (Serva, Feinbiochemica, Heidelberg) was used as such. Stock solution of the dye (30 mg) was made in methanol (5 ml) and then making up the volume to 100 ml with double-distilled water and stored in the dark.

A polyanionic polysaccharide material (DI)¹¹ was extracted from aqueous extract of Chalta (*Dillenia*

indica) fruit mucilage by repeated precipitation with ethanol.

Stoichiometry of polyanion-dye compound was determined¹² by conductometric titration of solutions of polyanions ($3.0 \times 10^{-7} M$) with the solution of PIC ($3.0 \times 10^{-4} M$).

Other methods followed including instrumentations were reported earlier².

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